

IPBES BBA Chapter 3 – Review of biodiversity assessment approaches (V2) / IPBES business and biodiversity assessment (3.1)

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1. Description

A review was conducted on 29 selected approaches out of 53 initially identified biodiversity assessment methods used by businesses and financial institutions to evaluate their biodiversity impacts. The term 'approach' encompasses frameworks, technical instruments (such as specific life cycle assessment models), and assessment systems that integrate both quantitative and qualitative methods.

Some of these biodiversity assessment approaches are part of broader systems that encompass other similar methods. The review aimed to identify patterns, commonalities, and differences among the approaches used for biodiversity impact assessment in the private sector. The findings form the basis for the observations and discussions presented in Chapter 3 of the methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

2. Process Overview

3. Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Search guided by expertise of project leader
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Google scholar
- **Search Date:** December 2023
- **Sample extracted:** 53 biodiversity assessment approaches identified

4. Review process

4.1. Collection of biodiversity assessment approaches to review (A)

Based on the expertise of the project leader, with support from two contributing authors. As team conducted an initial scoping review of biodiversity assessment approaches currently used by businesses and financial institutions. This resulted in an initial list of 53 biodiversity assessment approaches, which included some duplicates and outdated versions. From those biodiversity assessment approaches were selected as high priority based on the following criteria:

- The biodiversity assessment approaches were still in use in February 2024.
- There was enough information in the public domain to assess the methodology at the biodiversity assessment approaches.

The team selected a set of 21 high priority biodiversity assessment approaches for analysis

4.2. First round of analysis (February 2024) (R1)

- The team brainstormed categorizations (suggested use, intended users, method, data, output, scientific grounding) and assessed half of the prioritized biodiversity assessment tools independently. Assessments were recorded in an Excel spreadsheet using manuals, guidelines, peer-reviewed literature, and case studies.
- Contributing authors noted patterns and trends, such as inconsistent scientific backing and limited methodological disclosure, and prepared these observations for discussion.
- The team discussed review gaps and categorizations, refined the spreadsheet, and revised biodiversity assessment tools assessments for consistency.

4.3. Second round of analysis (March 2024) (R1)

- Contributing authors assessed the remaining half of prioritized biodiversity assessment tools and included a set of 10 additional biodiversity assessment tools from the initial list using updated categorizations.

- Contributing authors summarized new trends (e.g., frequent use of GLOBIO and life cycle analysis methodologies, consultancy links to metric disclosure issues) and prepared a document for discussion.
- The team addressed categorization issues (e.g., inconsistent units of measure) and updated relevant categories.

4.4. Third round of analysis (April 2024) (R1)

- The team revised the biodiversity assessment approaches with updated categorizations, removed superfluous columns, and created a final draft based on feedback. Two biodiversity assessment tools were excluded due to overlap, finalizing the list of assessment approaches. The review was cross-checked with peer-reviewed literature for consistency.
- Contributing authors updated key takeaways and patterns with recent observations.
- The team harmonized spreadsheet formatting created a summary file (B) with brief biodiversity assessment approaches descriptions and ensured communicability.

4.5. Final assessment tools review (May 2024)

- The final biodiversity assessment approaches were reviewed, along with the analysis of key takeaways and trends.
- Observations from the review formed the foundation for Chapter 3, discussing the state of biodiversity assessment in the private sector and presenting results from the biodiversity assessment approaches review.

5. Zotero Library

- A Zotero library (C) was created to gather all data sources and references used in the review process. Every source used for assessment of the biodiversity assessment tools has a note to indicate which tool it relates to. All data sources are also directly referenced in the Excel-file.
- Additional sources from peer-reviewed literature and reports were used to have accurate categorizations (list is available in C).
- Note that this library was used to conduct the business and biodiversity toll review in preparation for Chapter 3 of the IPBES business and biodiversity assessment, with the aim to provide necessary insights and understand the state of biodiversity assessments in the private sector.

Additional files

ID	Name	File Type	Size (KB)	Description
A	IPBES_BBA_3.1_2024_(A)	XLS	18 KB	Initial list of 53 biodiversity tools
R1	IPBES_BBA_3.1_2024_(R1)	XLS	88 KB	Excel file for categorizations and analysis tool of biodiversity assessment tools
B	IPBES_BBA_3.1_2025_(B)	XLS	22 KB	Summary of 29 biodiversity assessment tools
C	IPBES_BBA_3.1_2024_(C)	Bib	44 KB	Zotero library with References for biodiversity assessment tool and construction of categories